

PREFACE

Historical Connection for How Prime Numbers Relate to Philosophy

Pythagoras, Plato, Socrates, Euler, and Eratosthenes

—

Pythagoras of Samos lived from 570 BC to 490 BC and significantly influenced Philosophy and mathematics. What a wonder that is Pythagoras' Theorem.

Despite Pythagoras' great contributions to humanity, we have no writings that hail from him directly. All that we know about Pythagoras comes from his disciples.

Pythagoras led a society that was half-religious and half-scientific. His religious views became Pythagoreanism. His views were philosophical and religious in practice and his belief was that souls transmigrate (move from one body to another) after death, and that our souls are immortal and continue to be modified, forever, in another body. *

Pythagoras allegedly stated that numbers are important and have mystical significance.

Pythagoras was himself guided by two philosophers that also practiced mathematics and was introduced to mathematical ideas by Thales of Miletus and Anaximander of the same.

Plato of Athens, one of the most important philosophers to make substantial contributions to the field of philosophy and mathematics, lived from 427 BC to 347 BC.

As a philosopher, he came to appreciate the value of mathematics after he learned of the work of Pythagoras from Pythagoras' disciples.

Plato was inspired by the disciples of Pythagoras and began to understand and appreciate the connection between mathematics and philosophy. He heavily incorporated mathematics into his philosophical work.

Plato and Socrates lived during the same time. Both influenced each other a great deal and exchanged ideas. Socrates was also a philosopher, being one of the greatest philosophers of his time, and is known as the father of Western philosophy. Like Pythagoras, Socrates has no writings and all accounts hail from those who knew him.

Socrates was not a mathematician by trade, but did use mathematics as a tool to explore truth and philosophy. He also contributed greatly to the field of logic, producing a method of argumentation that uses a series of questions to expose ideas and expose contradictions. This is known as the *socratic method*.

To Plato once more. According to Plato himself (being that he wrote this directly), after being so strongly influenced by the disciples of Pythagoras, he stated:

“...that the reality which scientific thought is seeking must be expressible in mathematical terms, mathematics being the most precise and definite kind of thinking of which we are capable. The significance of this idea for the development of science from the first beginnings to the present day has been immense.”¹

If you have followed me so far, then we have several extremely important figures in the form of philosophers, most of whom were mathematicians that contributed greatly to the fields of mathematics, science, and philosophy, especially Western Philosophy.

Euclid of Alexandria lived later than both Socrates and Plato, from 325 BCE to 265 BCE. He is known as the "Father of Geometry" in Western mathematics and wrote *Elements*, one of the most influential mathematical texts in history. His work greatly suggested that he was guided by Plato's Philosophy.

Euclid's *Elements* laid the foundation for the work of Eratosthenes.

¹ MacTutor History of Mathematics. (n.d.). Plato. University of St Andrews. Retrieved January 29, 2025, from <https://mathshistory.st-andrews.ac.uk/Biographies/Plato/>

Now we arrive at Eratosthenes of Cyrene.

Eratosthenes lived from 276 BC to 194 BC and is regarded as the father of Geography and is known greatly for his work on prime numbers, which is described by the ancient algorithm he coined known as the sieve of Eratosthenes. This algorithm represented the first visual that would eventually become prime factorization.

Eratosthenes also dealt with the mathematics that underlie Plato's philosophy in one of his most important works, which has since been lost, *Plutonicus*.

—

Here, we see a development of thought, through time, involving great thinkers that used a blend of philosophy, mathematics, scientific thinking, and logic.

We also see that the principles of mathematics were deeply interwoven with philosophy, and that the mathematician who coined that ancient algorithm involving prime numbers also produced a work that used mathematics to explain Plato's Philosophy.

The last connection between these five people that I wish to make here hails from the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy and is located within the article *Platonism in the Philosophy of Mathematics*:

“Platonism about mathematics (or mathematical platonism) is the metaphysical view that there are abstract mathematical objects whose existence is independent of us and our language, thought, and practices. Just as electrons and planets exist independently of us, so do numbers and sets. And just as statements about electrons and planets are made true or false by the objects with which they are concerned and these objects' perfectly objective properties, so are statements about numbers and sets. Mathematical truths are therefore discovered, not invented.”²

Fun Fact - Both as irony and an ode to poetry, Plato was a nickname that translates, roughly, to “the broad”. This fun fact will make sense as this paper progresses.

² Linnebo, Øystein, "Platonism in the Philosophy of Mathematics", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Summer 2024 Edition), Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2024/entries/platonism-mathematics/>>.

Continued Below.

PREFACE CONT.

How Ideas Come to Light

Albert Einstein and Baruch Spinoza

—

“The more I read the Greeks, the more I realize that nothing like them has ever appeared in the world since.”

These were the words of Albert Einstein during an interview with Nicollo Tucci of the *New Yorker* magazine.

The year was 1879 when he was born and he left this world at the age of 76, in the year 1955.

One of many a groundbreaking discoveries by Einstein had been that which is the *Theory of Relativity*.

Einstein was no stranger to the use of philosophical ideas in his discoveries. His theory of relativity would have been unlikely if it were not for his utilization of philosophy in his methods, as evidenced by the following statement from Einstein concerning a book by David Hume titled *An Enquiry Concerning Human Understanding*, where Einstein read:

“...with eagerness and admiration shortly before finding relativity theory...[and] very possibly, I wouldn't have come to the solution without those philosophical studies”.³

The year was 1632 when Baruch de Spinoza (or Benedictus de Spinoza) was born. He left this world at the age of 44, in the year 1677.

Spinoza was inspired by the likes of Plato and Euclid. More on Euclid shortly.

According to the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy:

“...Spinoza is one of the most important philosophers—and certainly the most radical—of the early modern period.”⁴

So that we may stay oriented on this path I have created for us, I shall focus our attention purely on his method of deductive reasoning found in his seminal work, *The Ethics*.

Spinoza's *Ethics* is written in a style similar to that of Euclid, where we find the Geometric Method of Reasoning.

³ Stadler, Friedrich, ed. (2010). *The Present Situation in the Philosophy of Science*. Springer Netherlands. p. 349.

⁴ Nadler, Steven, "Baruch Spinoza", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2024 Edition), Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2024/entries/spinoza/>.

This method represents a style of proof where we orient the reader to the following chain of reasoning:

Definitions

Axioms

Propositions

Proofs

—

Where definitions are given, axioms are truths that can be proven, propositions represent that which is being investigated to be true, and proofs serve to prove the propositions.

For the purposes of this paper, I seek to engage you, the reader, in the same format used by Euclid and Spinoza, to support the claims that I am going to make.

It is here that I wish to guide you, as if it were by hand, to the understanding of what *consciousness* is.

Before I begin my treatise, I wish to briefly remark on the journey I have taken to get here, myself, with that wise word of philosophical content that served as the compass for my curiosities, said best by Spinoza in his *Ethics*:

“If the way which I have pointed out as leading to this result seems exceedingly hard, it may nevertheless be discovered. Needs must it be hard, since it is so seldom found. How would it be possible, if salvation were ready to our hand, and could without great labour be found, that it should be by almost all men neglected? **But all things excellent are as difficult as they are rare.**”

And so the saying goes.

—

THE
BEAUTY OF
REASON
AND HOW
CONSCIOUSNESS
COMES
TO BE

to

humanity.

PART I. CONCERNING CONSCIOUSNESS

DEFINITIONS

- I. By **idea**, I mean the mental conception which is formed by the mind as a thinking thing.
- II. By **attributive idea**, I mean that which the intellect perceives as constituting the essence of some initial idea.
- III. By **mode**, I mean that which is our unique internal environment, our idea medium, and that which produces subjective responses to ideas.
- IV. By **initial idea**, I mean that which is the initial thought that leads to branches of thought, or attributive ideas.
- V. By thoughts, I mean ideas about ideas, or in other words, thinking about thinking.
- VI. By experience, I mean the process about how ideas change over time based on interactions with other ideas.
- VII. By habits, I mean the progression of and association between ideas that lead to predictable results, repeatedly.
- VIII. By learning, I mean the process by which ideas begin forming associations between other ideas.
- IX. By reasoning, I mean the process of using known ideas to develop understanding.
- X. By understanding, I mean the precursor to intuition.
- XI. By intuition, I mean ideas that realize themselves by building off of known ideas.
- XII. By confusion, I mean the state where the ideas that form your reality do not align with that of objective reality.

AXIOMS

- I. Everything that exists, exists either in itself or in something else.
- II. That which cannot be conceived through anything else must be conceived through itself.
- III. From a given definite cause an effect necessarily follows; and, on the other hand, if no definite cause exists, it is impossible that an effect can follow. This loosely relates to Newton's Third Law, which states that for every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction.
- IV. No two ideas are exactly the same as there is no truly identical "anything" in the universe. Even seemingly identical objects will have minute differences when examined close enough. In fact, even two atoms of the same element can have slightly different states depending on their electron configuration, making them not completely identical.
- V. Pain, pleasure, and desire form the biological foundations of emotions, shaping the way emotions emerge and function at a fundamental level, providing the raw motivational forces that guide behavior.

I shall now, very simply and quickly enough for you to stare at my claims for a while, offer my proof of consciousness.

—

PROPOSITIONS

- I. If no two people have the same body, then no two people have the same idea medium whereby consciousness is produced. **This mode is what produces subjective responses** and that which is your idea medium is your internal environment that makes you, yourself.

Proof—This is neatly defined by (def. III) and (ax. IV).

- II. Contained in the information exchanged between you and your environment are ideas that are made up of their own individual ideas, ad infinitum.

Proof—Those thoughts, that you had, that which is you, and that which you are having now as you read; tell me, how do you know that you are having them? Further, how can you make sense out of these sentences that you, the wonderful reader who embarks on this journey with me, are reading? That is because each word itself is an idea, that is part of a sentence; a string of ideas, so to speak. As your mind reads this sentence, each words breaks down (i.e, gets processed) into **attributive ideas** that allow you to reason the meaning behind my words, which may or may not lead to understanding, depending on how you, as an individual person, subjectively respond to these ideas via the **mode** that comprises your body.

—

Now, reader, in the next proposition, I will visually represent in simple terms, a proof that I offer that seeks to explain what consciousness is, and why consciousness is subjective. Before I do, I must say this:

BEWARE

NOTE THAT THIS INFORMATION, ESPECIALLY IF IT IS TO BE TRUE, MAY SERVE TO THREATEN YOUR REALITY. IF YOU PROCEED, THEN YOU MAY NO LONGER THINK OF YOUR REALITY THE SAME AS YOU HAD PRIOR. PLEASE RECONSIDER IF YOU FEEL THAT THIS MAY THREATEN THAT WHICH YOU INTERPRET AS YOUR EXISTENCE.

Ahem—apologies for this abrupt and curious warning. I am simply aware that these ideas as I've presented them may lead to many an existential crisis.

If we are to proceed, then let us proceed, **ad infinitum**.

—

- III. Each original idea breaks down into an orderly set of attributive ideas that eventually lead to those ideas being broken down into our primal feelings via our mode that then dictate our subjective response. This response does not need to be something we are consciously aware of.

Proof—Seen using (def. I-V) and (ax. I-IV). That which causes an idea to appear in your mind—thus, conceived—is part of a process of reasoning by the mind and body. This process of reasoning by breaking ideas into attributive ideas and then to primal feelings is the body naturally tending toward order. Through this process, your brain attempts to remove any confusion about what something is not, in an objective sense, by guiding your reason towards understanding, so that intuition is developed. This makes much sense in the context of our biology—our body attempts to break things down into manageable chunks so as to not expend more energy than it needs to. This is a fact of surviving things. Things that are more energy efficient are more likely to survive.

Corollary I. —That things are more energy efficient are more likely to survive is not one to be missed. Let us expand upon this idea so that we may better process its meaning.

The striving towards simplicity—order—is all but common in nature. Take but the image of a flexible string that has a goal, a desire, to exist in the most energy efficient form possible. Now, for you Biologists, consider a protein, where we have some determinant of life existing among a sea of others. According to the Central Dogma of Biology, during translation, we find that this protein undergoes a process of folding and unfolding towards an established end. This process is orderly and follows a series of laws that guide this protein towards folding into its final confirmation. The final confirmation of this protein represents its most energetically favorable—energy efficient—form. The energy of this process is always conserved and proteins, all of the time, attempt to make this process as energetically efficient as possible, even if the process is not perfectly efficient.

I am now going to guide you through another thought experiment.

Corollary II. Now, this next thought experiment may take a bit of time to process and may lead to resistance in some, but I do suggest that you, just for the moment, drop that which you understand to be true, and allow yourself to expand the image of this thought in your mind. If what I am saying feels incorrect, then trust that you will be able to find yourself again when you become lost. To find ourselves, **we must accept unfamiliarity as familiar**. This is how we grow as a people.

Now, consider again that all ideas—all things—fundamentally strive towards order. Further, consider that all things have meaning, to us, though not intuitively the thing of themselves, especially if it is not living. Any interaction between two things, of any kind, produces energy by principle of Newton's Laws. All of his laws inherently involve energy, even if the equation does not explicitly state this. Newton's Laws of Motion, simply defined, are:

First Law (Law of Inertia) – An object at rest stays at rest, and an object in motion stays in motion at a constant velocity unless acted upon by an external force.

Second Law (Law of Acceleration) – The acceleration of an object depends on the force applied and the object's mass. Mathematically, $F = ma$ (Force = mass \times acceleration).

Third Law (Action-Reaction) – For every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction.

Where we can focus on the first and third law for the purpose of our demonstration.

When you throw Rock A at Rock B, the collision between these rocks produces energy, and, incidentally, one or both of the rocks split into some number of pieces. The energy initially came from you, the one who threw Rock A, and the energy was then transferred from Rock A to Rock B. The act of you throwing the rock, where our rock then travels in the air against the resistance of air, eventually colliding with Rock B, satisfies Newton's First Law, and the reaction that initially began with you throwing Rock A, then rock A with the air, and then Rock A between Rock B, satisfies Newton's Third Law of Motion. We also now see that Newton's Second Law is just as involved, as we must apply a force to Rock A, where our force is variable throughout the process of throwing Rock A, and thus Rock A accelerates while it is attached to us. After the rock leaves our hand, we are no longer involved in the act of accelerating it, but acceleration is still occurring (downward, of course) due to the force of gravity acting upon Rock A, bringing our rock down to the ground at an approximate rate of 9.8 m/s^2 . Since a force is acting upon the rock still, we see energy still existing as a factor.

Alright, alright, with all of the physical jargon out of the way, we see that energy is intricately involved in the process of throwing the rock and it eventually hitting the other. Considering that this process followed a series of Laws, we see that process adhering to order, where we find a thing, an idea, and by extension, everything, through its unique **mode**, breaking down ideas into ideas, into some "primary feeling", that which represents the energy expended, to produce a result, where the Laws of Physics—of the Universe—are adhered to therein. Therefore, according to the laws of

the Universe, **all things have feeling**, even the inanimate, and this feeling guides the process that represents our existence.

Since no two people are the same, the response that is produced, even when two people happen upon the same attributive ideas, is different. This is a fact of the universe and it must be so for us humans, for we are no better than this wonderful universe in which we reason to exist in.

That this response need not be something we are always consciously aware of can also be made rather obvious. Is a reflex not simply an immediate response that hinges upon your body quickly making sense of what may be potential danger? Your brain does not process this. Let's think about this with respect to something we have all experienced (I would assume); touching something hot and having this hot thing produce a reflex that which you are not consciously aware of.

As everything is an idea contained within another idea (ax. I), all that interacts with you, mind and body, are other ideas. According to our example, the ideas of this hot thing are leaving an impression on your body, and you on this hot thing as the cause of this interaction requires an effect (ax. III) that is the result of this interaction. Ultimately, the result of the impression of ideas left upon your body came from your body, very quickly, breaking down the idea of a hot thing into attributive ideas that then, very quickly, lead to a primal response that is rooted in our foundational feelings, pain, pleasure, and desire.

- IV. If ideas are themselves made up of ideas (def. I-II and ax. I-II) and if ideas break down into ideas (def. IV and ax. III), then we can consider some original idea to represent a multiple, and all that derives from it to be a factor. This means that we see a very clear relationship between the process whereby ideas break down into their attributes and the process that underlies prime factorization. Given the historical background set forth at the beginning of this paper, this connection makes sense.

Proof—I have (hopefully) neatly presented this in the following figures I created:

Here, we clearly see the process that our brain undergoes upon happening on an idea. It breaks things down, interconnectedly so that things don't get lost in the environment of thoughts; ideas anchor each other, so to speak, and as this process occurs, an image (a conception) is regarded in your mind as to what that idea means to you. Further, we see that attributive ideas can move back and forth between each other, but that each individual idea must break down into its own unique foundational feelings, where this combination of feelings produces a unique, subjective response (Prop. III) . **This is the process that represents consciousness, demystified.** Now, let us relate this to that ancient algorithm, so neatly grounded by Euclid and then expanded upon by Eratosthenes, an algorithm which has thus far served as my template, that algorithm known as prime factorization:

Where we have $2^1(5^2)(17^1) = \text{Response}$, where $\text{Response} = 850$.

In the context of this example, 850 represents our “original idea” and all that stems from it represents our attributive ideas, where we end up with numbers in the form of primes.

The attributes, much like that of the previous example, produce a response where the response is equal to its attributes. Unlike the previous example, numbers do not represent people, true; but numbers do represent ideas.

Where we can still explore this idea of subjectivity with even greater clarity. Say that you, the reader, and I, the writer, both thought of the idea of nuclear war.

If the response that we have is to be different by nature (ax. IV, prop. I), then we will naturally produce, if thought of in the context of a number, a different numerical result where the attributes that make up our number will be different.

Therefore, through Euclid and all the many a great mathematicians, we find the following:

That, since our attributes equal our response and since both represent ideas, that Ideas = Ideas.

A rather interesting proposition.

That which explains the processes which give rise to **consciousness**.

That which represents our subjective reality.

Where we see that consciousness is, quite literally, mostly a matter of perspective and, of course, our unique internal biological environment that serves as our idea medium. This strongly suggests that one’s reality can be almost definitively determined by the ideas that they encounter and that the less ideas that one has about something, such as in the case of children, the greater the impression.

One aspect of this proof that I see being challenged involves the nature of prime numbers being infinite and this existing in stark contrast to how our ideas break down into three foundational (primal) feelings.

Well, consider that any idea can proceed to infinity; even the idea of yourself. You mean something different to the squirrel than you do to the toad than you do to the many people that you likely encounter on any given day. In fact, not only can thinking things generate an idea, but their idea of you is dependent on how they begin seeing you differently with respect to time. Have we not met fickle people in our lives? How do we think of them? Is that constant? It is not; and therefore ideas themselves proceed to infinity.

Now, consider us once more. Our brain goes about the process of simplifying ideas into feeling.

This process is regarded as decluttering. When our brains do this, they are naturally tending towards an orderly state, as our bodies are seeking to conserve energy (ax. V, prop. III). This is why we don't see infinite attributive ideas when our brain has broken down the ideas we think into our foundational feelings.

The following graphic may explain this well. For the sake of clarity, "individual ideas" represent some set of ideas that branch off from one another over time. "Material ideas" represent that which gets broken down into feeling. Ideas ad infinitum represents the branching ideas as a concept beyond our body, moving towards infinity.

The ideas we interact with are themselves infinite, but the way we process them is not as they break down into foundational feeling responses. you can think of just a single idea when considering this diagram "material ideas" as represented in this figure represent those ideas that our brain breaks down over time, into foundational feelings.

- V. The efficiency of a response is determined by how quickly initial ideas are broken down into our foundational feelings. The faster this process occurs (and thus, the

better the quality of our attributive ideas), the more quickly we respond to something

Proof—the last illustrations allows us to visualize this process take place via prime factorization. If we chose to break 850 down into what we think to be intuitive based on the knowledge we have of divisibility at that time, then someone might break 850 down and devolve into numerical ramblings that do provide the values for attributes, but we might take longer to get to this point if we were less regarded in this practice. The less we understand, the lesser intuition we have about things (def. X), and the longer it takes for us to approach an objective–reality oriented–response.

VI. Fractals in nature provide us with the blueprints that represent the geometric orientation of our consciousness.

Proof—I thought this while looking at the vacillating trees. Fractals present in the branches. So orderly, yet masterfully abstract in craft. The process guiding this beauty also guides our consciousness. It is why, if you have followed my reasoning thus far, you may have felt a sense of alignment with my word. It is our geometrical nature as the intricate humans that we are that I seek to speak with. From this point, it should be clear that our ancestors have been seeking to do the same—to speak with us—to reason with us.

VII. Ideas interact with each other geometrically. REARRANGE POSITION

Proof—Ideas interact with each other in space. The distance between you and the ideas in this proof represents an external idea medium, so to speak. If ideas did not interact geometrically, then we would see that the laws of Physics—the physical laws that govern our universe—would be violated, as it would be impossible for you to see these words as the ideas that are photons that themselves carry ideas through the visual input of the text that you read would not be interpreted by you.

VIII. Since some initial idea can have a variety of attributive ideas, where the attributes are dependent on the person processing the information, then ideas with many attributes eventually split into ordered groups that represent fractals.

Proof—Since ideas interact geometrically (pos. VII), then an abundance of attributive ideas that then break down into the prime feelings will eventually find themselves clustered together into fractals. The following figure represents this process:

CONT.

To further bring reason to thought—consider this paper published in the journal *Scientific Reports*, titled *How neurons exploit fractal geometry to optimize their network connectivity* by Juliana H. Smith et al. The paper, especially if subsequent research has found it veritable, suggests that consciousness, the process that guides our thoughts and thus our conception, operates via fractals. In fact, as Euclid calls back to us, we find fractal patterns occurring, even in prime factorization:

256

$2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2$

625

$5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 5$

729

$3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$

—

—

people,

fractal.

together?

yes.

—

MOST IMPORTANT PART CONT. BELOW.

PART II. THE NATURE OF OUR REALITY

DEFINITIONS

- I. By **photon**, I mean a particle of light that reflects off of a surface or that can pass through each other, causing interference thereof. I also mean something without mass, but that possesses the qualities of mass through its ability to produce energy, and that also possesses qualities akin to that of a wave.
- II. By a **surface**, I mean that which can be seen or that which is interpreted to exist.
- III. By **fractal**, I mean that which has the quality of being infinite and self-repeating, that which begins as simple and tends towards complexity, that which possesses zoom symmetry, that which has fine or defined substance at small scales but cannot be discerned after exceeding its **visible limit of expansion**, that which is **affine** (**Euclid**, I found you), and that which exceeds our current topological dimension into that beyond a topological dimension of 3, and that which possesses entropy.
- IV. By **friction**, I mean **fractal friction** (the symbols for these shall be provided later) where the cause of all forms of friction arise by the interaction of two fractals with each other, resulting in **fractal interference**.
- V. By **fractal interference**, I mean **destructive** or **constructive fractal interference**.
- VI. By **destructive fractal interference**, I mean that which results from fractals that intersect and results in a decreasingly defined **substance**.
- VII. By **constructive fractal interference**, I mean that which results from fractals that intersect and result in an increasingly defined substance.
- VIII. By **substance**, I mean that which is—and always has been; that which is itself a surface.
- IX. By **consciousness**, henceforth, I mean that which is—interpreted; that is—all that produces a response that can be experienced by any object. Thus, I mean the consciousness of all things, animate and inanimate, where the determinant of consciousness is therefore **energy**.
- X. By **shadow**, I mean that which is the product of a light casting its nature onto a surface, where the shadow itself represents a **pure mathematical fractal**.
- XI. By **Universe**, I mean that which is the product of **affine transformation**, that which is itself a fractal and the source of all fractals that make up reality and thus our existence.

AXIOMS

- I. Most things that exist undergo a process that is optimized for energy efficiency.
- II. The **second law of thermodynamics** states that entropy acts as an opposing force to energy efficiency, that entropy represents disordered, turbulent randomness that always increases in an isolated system.

PROPOSITIONS

- I. All things that exist, undergo a process that is perfectly energetically efficient, where perfection is defined by the object's **mode**. The counter to absolute perfection, where we perceive inefficiency, is due to the concept that will be introduced in the second proposition. Thus, our perception that energy inefficiency exists is real insofar as it is a product of our mind, where the efficiency of our mind is itself determined by our mode, but that which is not objectively—that which pertains to reality—true.

Proof—that things are more energy efficient are more likely to survive is not one to be missed. Let us expand upon this idea so that we may better process its meaning.

The striving towards simplicity—order—is all but common in nature. Take the image of a flexible string that has a goal, a desire, to exist in the most energy efficient form possible. Now, for you Biologists, consider a protein, where we have some determinant of life existing among a sea of others. According to the Central Dogma of Biology, during translation, we find that this protein undergoes a process of folding and unfolding towards an established end. This process is orderly and follows a series of laws that guide this protein towards folding into its final confirmation. The final confirmation of this protein represents its most energetically favorable—energy efficient—form. The energy of this process is always conserved and proteins, all of the time, attempt to make this process as energetically efficient as possible, even if the process is not perfectly efficient.

I am now going to guide you through another thought experiment, though... I will say that. . .

...(.)this next thought experiment may take a bit of time to process and may lead to resistance in some, but I do suggest that you, just for the moment, drop that which you understand to be true, and allow yourself to expand the image of this thought in your mind. If what I am saying feels

incorrect, then trust that you will be able to find yourself again when you become lost. To find ourselves, **we must accept unfamiliarity as familiar**. This is how we grow as a people. In fact, the process of evolution would not have occurred without the mixing of the unfamiliar.

Now, consider again that all ideas—all things—fundamentally strive towards order. Further, consider that all things have meaning, to us, though not intuitively the thing of themselves, especially if it is not living. Any interaction between two things, of any kind, produces energy by principle of Newton's Laws. All of his laws inherently involve energy, even if the equation does not explicitly state this. Newton's Laws of Motion, simply defined, are:

First Law (Law of Inertia) – An object at rest stays at rest, and an object in motion stays in motion at a constant velocity unless acted upon by an external force.

Second Law (Law of Acceleration) – The acceleration of an object depends on the force applied and the object's mass. Mathematically, $F = ma$ (Force = mass \times acceleration).

Third Law (Action-Reaction) – For every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction.

Where we can focus on the first and third law for the purpose of our demonstration.

When you throw Rock A at Rock B, the collision between these rocks produces energy, and, incidentally, one or both of the rocks split into some number of pieces. The energy initially came from you, the one who threw Rock A, and the energy was then transferred from Rock A to Rock B. The act of you throwing the rock, where our rock then travels in the air against the resistance of air, eventually colliding with Rock B, satisfies Newton's First Law, and the reaction that initially began with you throwing Rock A, then rock A with the air, and then Rock A between Rock B, satisfies Newton's Third Law of Motion. We also now see that Newton's Second Law is just as involved, as we must apply a force to Rock A, where our force is variable throughout the process of throwing Rock A, and thus Rock A accelerates while it is attached to us. After the rock leaves our hand, we are no longer involved in the act of accelerating it, but acceleration is still occurring (downward, of course) due to the force of gravity acting upon Rock A, bringing our rock down to the ground at an approximate rate of 9.8 m/s^2 . Since a force is acting upon the rock still, we see energy still existing as a factor.

Alright, alright, with all of the physical jargon out of the way, we see that energy is intricately involved in the process of throwing the rock and it eventually hitting the other. Considering that

this process followed a series of Laws, we see that process adhering to order, where we find a thing, an idea, and by extension, everything, through its unique **mode**, breaking down ideas into ideas, into some “primary feeling”, that which represents the energy expended, to produce a result, where the Laws of Physics—of the Universe—are adhered to therein. Therefore, according to the laws of the Universe, **all things have feeling**, even the inanimate, and this feeling guides the process that represents our existence. How does that make you feel? Pleasure?...Desire? Pain?

- II. All things that exist, do so because of fractal expansion. Fractal expansion of a perfect fractal can be demonstrated by anyone, at any time. Fractal expansion also represents the nature of the Universe and dictates the passage of time. The speed of the universe can also be determined by the expansion of a **pure mathematical fractal**, where anything that produces a shadow—(def. X)—is capable of producing a pure mathematical fractal, where this fractal, and thus the speed of universal expansion, moves at the speed of light.

Proof—I’ll address this in reverse. We know that the speed of light represents the speed that light travels in a vacuum, where this speed is defined as 299,792,458 metres per second. If all things that exist, exist either in itself or in something else (part I. ax. I), then all that is within the Universe represents a **substance** within a vacuum, and is therefore subject to this speed. A **shadow**, by definition of it being the **product of light** (def. I, def X) possesses no mass, and possesses the same wave-like properties as the edges of a shadow’s penumbra appear to merge due to the properties of light acting as a wave, causing interference. Is the penumbra not just the

- III. All things represent a fractal, a thing within a thing within a thing, even time (**time and time again**). Even light.

Proof—If a fractal, as provided by (part II. def. III) is defined as such—where it clearly is—and if everything exists, exists within itself or in something else; if what cannot be conceived through anything else must be conceived through itself; if from a definite cause, an effect must follow and if no definite cause exists, then it is impossible that an effect can follow—(part I. ax. I-III), then all things—from the composition of lesser forms of matter to greater forms of matter; from the expansion of a balloon by heat; to the radiation that produces heat and even the heat itself—represents a series of fractals, where the composition of the fractal determines its **mode**—it’s unique composition where no identical replicate exists—and therefore determines its essential nature as a thing, that which is unique and, of course, subjective.

PROOF CONT. BELOW

In fact, even the patterns that guide our habits represent our nature as fractal beings. Habit patterns represent an abstract form where the chain of events that lead to a habit being performed act as a thing within itself, where (part I. proof II.) the breakdown of the idea that you thought, that day at that time, that which determined the course of action that you chose to take, **with respect to time**, initially began as simply one idea that branched off into a series of ideas through the **mode** that is your unique self, producing some series of pain, pleasure, and desire, that then equated into a response that represent your **qualia**.

IV. All things that exist, do so against **fractal entropy**, what I define here, specifically, as the nature of **Universal expansion**, where the expansion of the Universe is guided by a perpetual process of fractals expanding or coming to a halt, where fractal expansion comes to an apparent halt at the **speed of light**, and at **absolute zero**.

As I currently feel satisfied with the questions I sought to solve, I will stop my writings on the matter here.

As a society, we all should strive to see the best in each other. To seek alignment as a society is to become a friend to the people who can realize themselves in you. When we hold that mirror to our face, what ideas do we hold about what we see?

And to all a beautiful day, with much embrace and gracious warm-ing.

ad infiniti

—

